

GENERAL INVESTIGATION OF NUMERATIVE PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS “ONE” AND “TWO” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8068010>

Abstract.

The article discusses the importance of using new pedagogical methods in physical education classes and the advantages of physical education classes in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: education, ethics, physical education, style, methodology, student, athlete.

INTRODUCTION

Sports opportunity. Sport is the most effective way to introduce a country to the world. A combination of sports, beauty, honesty and health. Most of the opportunities created in our country are dedicated to sports. Taking into account that the highest results are given to sports competitions before the Science Olympiads, we teachers have a huge task to popularize science among young people and to deliver sports champions. In the course of the article, we want to talk about the methods that are effectively used to achieve such a good result.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Here, while paying attention to some textbooks, we come across information about the methods used in physical education. In particular, examples of methods are presented in the textbooks "Theory and Methodology of Physical Education" by R.S.Salomov, A.K.Sharipov and "Theory and Methodology of Physical Education" by S.R.Salomov. For example, in the textbook, while talking about the method of visualization, the following information is given about the method. It is noted that this method is widely used in physical education. That is, by affecting all the senses, communication with existing things is established. It uses sight, movement and other senses. These methods are divided into the following groups using a set of methods based on the characteristics of the exercises and performance conditions in the implementation of demonstration in a broad sense. They consist of methodical demonstration by the teacher or with the help of a student.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In order to form initial ideas about the effect of movement and the rules of performing the exercises, auxiliary means of demonstration, i.e. the direct demonstration method, are widely used. Such direct demonstration methods are divided into:

- display of pictures, diagrams, photographs and similar visual aids; Demonstration of product models and layouts;
- Movie and VCR show;
- Selected - using devices, for example: microphone,
- radio equipment, electric light signals;

- Directed sensory movement methods (for example, exercises);
- Orientation (goal) methods (hanging balls, flags, signs in halls and grounds, etc.).
- Leader and daily sensor planned methods;
- Quick information method (VCR).

We will fully analyze the essence of sports through the following story. "Compared to others, Sunnatillo's upbringing is a bit more difficult. After his father left for another woman, negative characters began to appear in his upbringing.

He was gripped by the idea that everything in life is taken by force.

As a result, he used his physical abilities instead of his mind. One day he tried to steal. Violence, theft, and adultery became normal for him. In doing so, he took advantage of the opportunities he gained by training his physical strength a little.

The physical education teacher noticed these changes of Sunnatillo, who was studying with excellent grades. And to turn the young man away from this path, he used a special method."

The fact that Sunnatillo had already entered this street, these habits were absorbed into his blood, made it difficult to change him. But this method of the pedagogue helped him a lot. Method's first plan encouraged him verbally, that is, Sunnatillo's favorite sport is wrestling, and he said that to achieve great success in football, he only needs to practice, and he hopes that he will become a great athlete in the future. After the first victory, Sunnatillo started training. Despite the fact that he took all his pains from sports, his teacher told him that sports is a friendship, a door of opportunities, a beginning of kindness. His victories in sports and the support of his teacher changed him in a positive direction. Now he has become a breadwinner who takes care of his brothers and supports his mother.

Yes, compared to other subjects, teaching methods in physical education classes are fundamentally different. In the process of physical education, the main activity of the teacher is carried out with words: with the help of words, knowledge is imparted, understanding is activated and deepened, tasks are assigned, their execution is controlled, results are analyzed and evaluated, children are disciplined. The word solves the necessary task in understanding, evaluating and self-managing the activities of those involved.

In addition, the word consists of one or another dedicative story, conversation, discussion, etc., depending on its use.

The word method: 1) giving instructions; 2) additional explanation; 3) instructions and orders; 4) oral assessment; 5) self-talk and self-command; 6) encouragement, 7) verbal abuse; 8) general order; 9) analysis; 10) Verbal interaction In addition, giving instructions is also one of the effective methods. In this case, conveying concrete and clearly understandable rules for performing tasks or exercises to those involved in the technique learning activity.

In the additional explanation method, some actions or methods of execution are interpreted and explained through various exhibitions in order to provide deeper knowledge in order to improve the quality of the execution method.

Management of students' activities in the form of special words in instructions and commands. Pre-showing through instructions and commands is used to define tasks and is one of the most effective methods.

CONCLUSION

Sport, which unites the countries of the world with the ideals of friendship, health, honesty, kindness, is not only a science, but a vital necessity of **ABSTRACT**

This article is devoted to the study of the numerative phraseological units. In this article we try to define the word phraseology and its isolation from lexicology. In order to comprehend the word phraseologism they first introduced it to the scholars, who made their initial attempt to study this field of linguistics, which is called phraseology. In this article the basic types of phraseological units are analyzed relating to the degree of idiomaticity in the process of learning a foreign language. The authors have tried to define the types of phraseological units by using numerous examples.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена исследованию возникновения нумеративной фразеологии. В данной статье авторы уточняют определения слова фразеология и его обособления от лексикологии. Для понимания слова фразеологизм мы обратились к работам учёных, которые предприняли свою первоначальную попытку изучить область лингвистики, которую мы называем фразеологией. В данной статье анализируются основные типы фразеологических единиц, относящиеся к степени идиоматичности в процессе изучения иностранного языка. Авторы попытались определить типы фразеологических единиц с помощью примеров.

Key words: vocabulary, language, phraseology, study, stylistic, phraseological units, word-group, style, origin, idiom, stability, phraseological fusions, phraseological units, phraseological collocations.

Ключевые слова: лексика, язык, фразеология, исследование, стилистика, ФЕ, словосочетание, стиль, происхождение, идиома, устойчивость, фразеологические сращения, фразеологические единства, фразеологические словосочетания.

INTRODUCTION

Language is an important element of the culture of any nation, including the fact that the language reflects the culture, the history of the nation and the ideology and world view of the nation. Many units of the language can be such a mirror, but there are some language units, which by their very nature can be the better mirror of the culture, history and world view of the nation. One of these language units is a phraseological unit.

Phraseology of each language makes a significant contribution to the formation of figurative pictures of the world. Knowing the phraseology allows to get a deeper understanding of the history and character of the people. Phraseologisms exist in close connection with vocabulary. Their study helps to get better understanding of the vocabulary structure, education and the use of lexical units in speech. When we talk about this term, our tongue instantly curves into another notion that signifies the above concept.

Phraseological units are special language means in which the originality and uniqueness of any language is concentrated. Considering phraseological unit in this aspect, we come to the disclosure of the 'phraseology' concept in the broad sense of the word. In a narrow sense, phraseology is a section of linguistics that studies stable speech speed [3, p. 942].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We used a complex method of analysis, including:

- 1) method of semantic analysis involves the analysis of cultural values of the numbers;
- 2) descriptive method comprises monitoring and classification of the material;
- 3) comparative analysis identifies the universal and distinctive features of numerals in unrelated languages;

4) method of sampling from different phraseological, defining, bilingual dictionaries by the criterion of existence of the numeral component in the linguistic unit.

For the first time, the concept of phraseological unit was formulated by the linguist S. Balli, a representative of the French school of linguistics. He called the phraseological unitas 'combinations that have firmly entered the language' [4, p. 380]. English and American researchers such as L.P. Smith, A. Mackay, J. Seidlou, and W. McMordi use the term 'idiom' in their writings on the study of phraseological unit. By an idiom they mean an expression whose value is not inferred from the value of its individual elements.

The richness of vocabulary of every language depends on not only the ways of forming new words, but also on the permanent idioms it may form. The science which studies the 'world' of those units is called phraseology. Phraseology is the science about idioms, and it was firstly used in 1928 by Y.D. Polovinov. [1, p. 208]

Phraseology resembles a picturesque gallery comprising the samples of eternal and marvelous customs and traditions of a nation, historical memorials, fairy tales and songs. Phraseology is not only the most colourful part of vocabulary, but also the most democratic layer.

For the first time, phraseology was used in the study of literature. While translating some fiction from one language into another it became impossible to translate inseparable word combinations. Then the phraseological unities in those languages were researched. Although the biggest part of phraseological materials is included in vocabulary and other sources, the research works on the theory of phraseology have been rarely met in the sources concerning linguistics as L. Smith, D. Curry, W. Ball, Ch. Bally. Up to now the matters of English phraseology have been studied within grammar, stylistics, lexicography and the history of language.

Later phraseology has been studied as a branch of lexicology. As the linguistics developed, nowadays phraseology has been admitted and is being researched as an independent branch of linguistics in most languages. It is worth pointing out that a number of Eastern European and Russian scholars researched this field in their works. A lot of results were achieved. Though French scholar Charlie Bally put the term phraseology into the science, this term wasn't used in the works of Western European and American linguists. Bally uses phraseology within stylistics. The matter of studying phraseology as an independent branch of linguistics was advanced by Russian linguist E.D.Polivanov. As he maintains positively, lexis studies separate words' meanings, morphology studies words' structure, syntax studies the structure of word combinations. In his opinion, there is a necessity for an independent field which studies peculiar unique word combinations. E.D.Polivanov was sure that phraseology would become firmly fixed in linguistics and it occurred. The matter of studying phraseology as a separate branch of linguistics was promoted by Russian scholar V.V.Vinogradov too. V.V.Vinogradov's great service is that he separated phraseological unities into semantic groups. However, phraseology remained a part of lexicology, because the principal criteria proving that phraseology could be an independent field of linguistics hadn't been worked out yet. So, phraseology was being learned as the part of lexicology. After E.D.Polivanov and V.V.Vinogradov the first who promoted the idea of studying phraseology independently was scholar B.A.Larin. He affirmed that enough scientific research hadn't been done in phraseology. In Russian linguist A.V.Kunin's opinion, phraseology came off the lexicology circle: its range and significance have been raised. Though a lot of, sometimes

controversial ideas were expressed concerning phraseology a number of scientific research works had been done. Such outstanding linguists as N.N. Amosova, A.V.Kunin, V.A.Smirnitsky, S.S.Gorelik, V.L. Arkhangelsky, V.V. Vinogradov, B.A. Larin, M.E.Umarhodjayev, I.A. Melchuk, I.I. Revzin, S.N.Savitskaya, Yu.D. Apresan have great services to this science.[1, p. 210]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers have entered our lives so long ago that we do not even pay attention to it. They surround us everywhere, but it's just information that conveys to our consciousness some kind of messages.

There we must note that in such idiom this numeral takes clear negative connotations as "not enough", "too little" in comparison with a "standard" (two hands, capability to several different tricks, etc.). The numeral "one" is in some cases contrasted to the numeral "two", both numerical component is not usually used in their specific meaning. "Two" expresses a certain set, "one" means the absence of a set. But there are idioms where "one" is opposed to "nothing" and there it takes a positive (or at least not negative) connotations. For example: *In the land of the blind, the one-eyed man is king — if surrounded by people less capable or able, someone who would not normally be considered special can shine.*

In very rare cases this numeral can take an additional meaning "the beginning of a sequence". The rareness of this meaning is rather peculiar, since this numeral appeared to be a beginning of a sequence (one, two, three, etc.). We can presume that the cause of this rareness is that this word is used as a pronoun more often than as a numeral in speech. But we find an example:

One good turn deserves another — when people do something good, something good will happen to them; one fire drives out another — to remove the results of some action with the same action;

There is another meaning of this numeral, which is close to the opposition "small number" — "infinitely large number", but it has some additional aspects. This meaning is represented in the idioms: *one-man band — when one person does all the work or has all the responsibility somewhere, then they are a one-man band; one over the eight — very drunk (more than eight). One in a thousand — very rare and precious.* Here we can recall the Uzbek proverb «*Yolg'iz o'tning change chiqmas, Changi chiqsa ham dong'i chiqmas*» (compare to English one man no man), to which all these idioms are opposite. The Uzbek proverb means that "one" is always less than "many", but in this English idioms we can see that in some aspects "one" can be more than "many", though not all of these aspects are good or healthy. [1, 27] One of the most common meanings of the numeral "one" appearing in the idioms is the meaning "very fast". Though this meaning exists not exceptionally in English linguo-culture (for example, Uzbek *bir zarb bilan — very fast, in one move*), it seems very interesting, since the concept of number here corresponds with the concept of movement or time. Such meaning development became possible due to the figurative meaning of the words, and here it based on metaphorical shift of meaning.

One fell swoop — a single hasty action or occurrence; with one stroke of the pen — very fast, with a single action. We should pay particular attention to the frequent juxtaposition in English phraseological unit of "one" and "another" V 'the other', for example: *one man may steal a horse while another may not look over a hedge — people may take different degrees of liberty depending on our opinion of them; in (at) one ear and out at the other — if information*

goes in one ear and out the other the person who is told it forgets it immediately because he does not listen carefully enough. Some examples in Uzbek for number "one": *"Muhabbat bitta – ko'z tortta", "O'ntaning yor-yori bo'lguncha, Bittaning vafodori bo'l", "Kelining bitta bo'lsa, o'tirib yeysan, Ikkita bo'lsa, turib yeysan, Uchta bo'lsa, yurib yeysan, To'rtta bo'lsa, yorg'alab yeysan", "Erning Yoshi ikki o'ttiz, Bittasini urdik biz", "O'nta o'g'lim bo'lguncha, bitta cholim bo'lsin", "O'g'ri bitta, gumon mingta"*.

The meaning of phraseology is not deduced from the value of the sum of its elements, but is determined by rethinking. This is because the phraseological phrase is not a free phrase, but one of its main properties is reproducibility. So the free combinations are the expressions *'one horse', 'seven girls', 'two pillows'*, which are created from separate words in the process of communication, at the same time, the expressions *'one-horse town', 'two left feet', 'seventh heaven', 'take five'* are phraseological units that are retrieved from the memory just like individual words. Any violation in the syntactic or semantic structure of this phraseological unit irreparably leads to the loss of their meaning.

Sometimes this opposition is only implied, for example: one side of the medal — one side of a coin, one aspect of a person's character or of any business, event, object; friendship cannot stand always on one side — friendship must be mutual or it is not friendship. This opposition between "one" / "another" ("the other") complicates the value of a numeric component and separates it from the specific value of a numeral. There are several main additional meanings, which the numeral "one" can get when it is used in the phraseological unit. [2, 23]

The numeral "two" goes back to the Old English word *twa* "two". According to the Collins English Dictionary, this word has several meanings: the cardinal number that is the sum of one and one; a numeral, 2, II, (ii), etc, representing this number; something representing, represented by, or consisting of two units, such as a playing card with two symbols on it.

So we can see that this numeral in its most common meaning denotes duality, the fact that something consists of the two parts (a sum of one and one). But in the idioms this duality often means the lack of unity: *fall (sit) between two stools* — if something falls between two stools, it fails because it is neither one type of thing nor another and if someone falls between two stools, they fail because they try to combine two different types of thing that cannot be combined.

The meaning "duality" can represent also some negative concepts, for example the double danger or double mishaps: *between two fires* — difficult / painful situation without any escape; *one-two punch* — two unpleasant things that happen together; The uncertainty: *be in two minds* — be unable to decide about something; which also can be expressed by means of the negation of "two", if "two" implies "uncertainty, choice", so "not two" naturally implies "certainty, absence of choice": (there's) no two ways about it — something that you say in order to emphasize that something is true. [12, 47]

According to the temporary conclusion, we may point out that in several phraseological units the numerals "one" and "two" can be used as synonyms ("very few", "very fast", "duality as unity") or as antonyms ("unity vs. duality"). Besides there are several meaning that are distinctive for each numeral. Some examples in Uzbek for number "two": *"Ikkiko'chgan – birtanlangan", "Bir bosh – balo bosh, Ikki bosh – mardona bosh"*,

“Yolg’izaqlo’ziyaxshi, Ikkibo’lsa, yanayaxshi”, “Ikkiovsinningkavushi, Kavshandozda ham chandishar”, “Xonbirbo’lsa, el tuzalar, Ikkibo’lsa, yurt buzilar”.

It has been repeatedly pointed out that word-groups analyzed as functionally and semantically inseparable units are considered to be the subject matter of phraseology. It should be noted that proper scientific investigation of English phraseology has not been attempted until quite recently. English and American linguists tried to collect various words, word-groups and sentences by presenting some features of view, style, origin and usage which are peculiar to them. These units are usually described as idioms but no attempt has been made to analyze these idioms as a separate class of linguistic units.

However, the existing terms, [4, p. 480] such as set-phrases, idioms, word-equivalents reflect to a certain extent the main debatable issues of phraseology. The term set-phrase implies that the basic criterion of differentiation is the stability of lexical components and grammatical structure of word-groups. The term idioms generally imply that the essential feature of the linguistic units under consideration is the idiomaticity or lack of motivation.

Phraseological units are habitually defined as non-motivated word-groups that cannot be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as a ready-made system. This definition proceeds from the assumption that the essential features of phraseological units are considered to be the stability of the lexical components. [3, p. 942] It is frequently assumed that unlike components of free word-groups which may vary due to the needs of communication, words of phraseological units are reproduced as single unchangeable collocations.

Taking into account mainly the degree of idiomaticity phraseological units may be classified into three big groups: phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations.

Phraseological fusions are completely non-motivated word-groups, such as **one-horse town**- *“a town or village that is very small. The image is that nothing ever happens in the town: it is boring and quiet”*; **two left feet** -*“having a terrible coordination in one’s movements and terrible balance”*; **take five** -*“take a short break”* and the like. The meaning of the components has no connections whatsoever, at least synchronically, with the meaning of the whole group. Idiomaticity is, as a rule, combined with complete stability of the lexical components and the grammatical structure of the fusion.

Phraseological unities are partially non-motivated as their meaning can usually be perceived through the metaphoric meaning of the whole phraseological unit. For example, **to be very, very happy about something, have a drink before leaving** if interpreted as semantically motivated through the combined lexical meaning of the component words would naturally lead one to understand these in their literal meaning. The metaphoric meaning of the whole unit, however, readily suggests **‘seventh heaven’** or **‘on cloud nine’** for *to be very, very happy about something* and **‘one for the road’** for *wash have a drink before leaving*. Phraseological unities are as a rule marked by a comparatively high degree of stability of the lexical components.

Phraseological collocations are motivated but they are made up of words possessing specific lexical valency which accounts for a certain degree of stability in such word-groups. In phraseological collocations variability of member words is strictly limited. For instance, **bear a grudge** may be changed into **bear malice**, but **not into bear a fancy or liking**. We can say **take a liking (fancy)** but **not take hatred (disgust)**. These habitual collocations tend to

become kind of clichés where the meaning of member-words is to some extent dominated by the meaning of the whole group. Due to these phraseological collocations are felt possessing a certain degree of semantic inseparability.

CONCLUSION

So, numbers are known to be an integral part of the ethnic culture of Uzbek and English languages, their relation in social interaction depicted by special and 'traditional' numbers by rendering cumulative function. Thus, every language has its numbers with their specific meaning and quality. Whatever language is Uzbek West countries, all of them are greatly interested in the analysis of their specific features and usage areas. They are able to employ phrases in reference to their aims and meanings. Every digit has its educating significance and special place. Every number in Uzbek language which is known to be bears educative meaning in additional to its main function.

To conclude the article, it can be reviewed that by taking into consideration the degree of idiomaticity phraseological units are classified into three groups such as phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations. [2, p. 125] They are differentiated according to their idiomaticity and they are proven with the examples.

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